

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Events promoting ownership of solutions Deliverable 5.6

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Author(s)	Giles Rickard (WRT)
Contributors	Amaya Soto (CETMAR), Andrea Ogando (UVIGO), Pauline Guérécheau-Desvignes (ADEME), Manuela Puddu (MEDSEA), Francesca Etzi (MEDSEA), Evrydiki Pavlidi (MOG), Sanna Varis (LAPP)
Primary Contact and Email	Giles Rickard giles@wrt.org.uk
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Focus of this Deliverable

Ownership of solutions were promoted in the different demonstrators predominantly through events and workshops with stakeholders, including landowners, community groups and local authorities. A pattern here was that engagement and ownership around the solutions was often best when there was early and continued engagement with stakeholders through the development phase of solutions. The final events provide a good opportunity to showcase delivered solutions with more meaningful examples that can be shared with key stakeholders and to wider communities, to raise awareness and build ownership. The variation in engagement across the demonstrators highlights the benefit of a flexible approach, so that engagement and ownership can be bespoke to the region. For some solutions and regions local authorities are the key owner of solutions going forward, whereas in other regions, engaging businesses and a range of stakeholders at different levels is key.

1.0 Introduction

Focus of this Deliverable

The D5.6 report is intended to evidence and briefly review the events promoting the ownership of solutions by the different demonstrators. These were designed to promote the solutions to wider, landowners' community groups and local authorities to increase their continued uptake.

Deliverable contents

There is no specific reporting required through this deliverable; however, the document provides a place to evidence these events in the demonstrators such as photos, agenda's and the talks/items covered.

2.0 Demonstrator Event Summaries

1.1 WRT Westcountry Region, UK demonstrator – East Devon Resilience event

The East Devon Resilience event was run on the 2nd of August and provided a showcase opportunity to present on TransformAr and other related resilience action in the area linked to WRT. There was also the opportunity for a local community group to present on the work they are doing locally.

This provided the opportunity to bring in a wider audience and sets of stakes holders, particularly active community groups active in the area.

<https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/east-devon-resilience-showcase-tickets-1490831750899?aff=oddtcreator>

East Devon Resilience event Agenda

Time	What	Who
10:30-10:45	Arrival and networking	All
10:45-10:50	Introduction	Zoe Connelly / Helen Staddon
10:50-11:10	TransformAR	Giles Rickard
11:10-11:30	Enforce	Francis Rowney / Finely Gibson
11:30-11:45	Coffee break	
11:45-12:05	RRTU	Emily Hobson-Martin
12:05-12:25	Community case study	Vicky Whitworth / Paul Spearing
12:30-13:30	Lunch	
13:30-15:00	Carousel sessions	All – 5x 15 minute sessions 1: TransformAR climate adaptation techniques – GR 2: RRTU – EH-M 3: Enforce – FR / FG 4: INNWATER questions (CSI) – ZC 5: RRC / ARSINOE - RH NR, IW, HS to float between tables

Overview of Activity

After arrival and introductions TransformAr was presented first, with Giles Rickard presenting on project findings including updated climate change scenarios looking forward, the Nature based solutions utilized and identified through the co-creation workshops, an update on nutrient neutrality and how it may be able to fund adaption going forward. There was also an overview of the bankability work and potential investment models designed through D5.3. This was followed by a summary of the key findings from TransformAr.

Francis Rowney and Finely Gibson from University of Exeter presented on the Enforce project and covered the role satellite imagery to identify potential areas of soil erosion and risk and how tracing sources of sediment loss and erosion can be used to bring about water quality and flow improvements.

Emily Hobson-Martin presented on the Rivers Run Through Us (RRTU) which is a lottery funded and community focused project, looking into the history of the river and the changes in land use and river type of the years. It also highlight the restoration work that is planned including management of invasive weeds such as Himalayan balsam.

Vicky Whitworth then presented from Kit Brook River Restoration about the work they have delivered as a local community group and ongoing water quality monitoring that they have undertaken to help identify river health and potential sources of pollution.

For the afternoon part of the event, after lunch and networking a carousel session was set up so that attendees could spend 15 minutes with each speaker, each of which had a set of materials and posters on the table including printed photos to discuss project findings and solutions. This enabled stakeholder to ask more detailed questions and have more in-depth discussions.

TransformAr presentation highlights

Summary

- Hotter summers and warmer winters -> extension of the vegetation period and increasing water vegetation demand (EvapoTranspiration)
- Wetter winters and drier summers -> drier soils in summer, more water stress, but in winter increase in groundwater recharge leading to more water in rivers (also in summer)
- More intense precipitation -> increase in flood number and intensity, more surface runoff, more erosion and phosphorous losses. Riparian zones and wetlands to counteract
- Longer vegetation period -> two crops? But wetter soil conditions in spring and fall may lead to problems with cultivation. Increasing Temperature/vegetation period may foster biotic risks (Pest and diseases)
- More vegetation in winter -> May lead to more nutrient (nitrate) uptake and reduce losses with percolation. Cover crops in winter are important.
- Higher water temperatures in rivers -> stimulate algae growth and blooming
- Cropping and fertilization schemes have to be adapted accordingly

TransformAr- scope of talk

TransformAr Accelerating and Upscaling transformational adaptation

- Project Background
- Climate change scenarios
- Nature-based Solutions
- Nutrient neutrality
- Bankability and Investment Models
- Summary of findings

Westcountry Rivers Trust - Summary

TransformAr Key findings

Climate challenges – Wetter winters and drier summers, higher water temperatures, greater intensity of rain

NBS –Adaption Pathways – Adaption solutions and pathways available, benefit from wider acceptance and evidence base

Nutrient Neutrality – slow but actions outlined and formation of credits taking place

Upscaling, bankability and Investment – Benefit from government leadership and framework/regulation – some investment moving forward

1.2 CETMAR Galicia demonstrator

The promotion of ownership of the Galician solutions was embedded into the demonstrator process from the very beginning, using multiple complementary methods rather than being limited to a single event.

Overview of the activities

Initial Co-Design and Engagement

Bilateral visits were carried out with farmers' associations and guilds, as well as with other relevant stakeholders, including producer organisations, local administrations, and research institutes. During these visits, a co-design process was proposed. Feedback was gathered throughout the entire process to ensure continuous adjustments that met stakeholders' requirements.

As a first step, a set of minimum requirements was jointly defined, addressing both the daily operational needs of field producers and the scientific and technological needs of research and innovation actors.

Implementation and Continuous Monitoring

Here, we distinguish between the two digital and technological solutions (Mussel Raft Monitoring - MRM- and Intertidal Monitoring –INTERM-) and the management solution (the Resilience Index -RI-) While the RI required more desk-based analysis, the implementation of the digital-technological solutions (RI and INTERM) also entailed frequent field monitoring visits and meetings (4-6 participants average).

In addition, coordination meetings with Galician stakeholders involved in the demonstrator were held approximately every 2–3 months, or whenever necessary, to adjust activities in response to next steps and specific reported situations.

The following table summarises the coordination meetings organised between 2022 and 2025:

No.	Date	No.	Date
1	06/05/2022	8	30/10/2023
2	12/06/2022	9	21/02/2024
3	07/07/2022	10	18/03/2024
4	16/11/2022	11	29/04/2024
5	18/04/2023	12	22/07/2024

6	27/06/2023	13	13/09/2024
7	10/09/2023	14	02/04/2025

Key Events Strengthening Ownership

Beyond regular workshops dedicated to building the pathways and the action plan, four major events played a significant role in reinforcing the ownership of the Galician solutions:

DATE	EVENT	PARTICIPANTS	PURPOSE
25/04/2024 & 03/04/2025	National Climate Change working groups workshops - Online - In person - Madrid	34 23	TransformAr presentation in the first meeting to share information and coordinate at national level with projects working for the study of the effect of CC impact on aquaculture. The second meeting was to bring insights and contribute to the National Plan for Climate Change (Deputy Directorate General of Aquaculture, Fishery Marketing, and Structural Actions) Agenda and report internally available at CETMAR (TransformAr-Meetings 2025)
24/05/2024	Consultation Workshop	28	Share and review project results, particularly the resilience index. The workshop gathered participants representing the quintuple helix of the Galician clam and mussel sectors. Full report available at TransformAr Sharepoint WP3/Task 3.1/Galicia Consultation WS INFORME-DINAMICA-TALLER vf.pdf
18/09/2024	Open Day	35	Return and discuss analysed data, foster debate on implications, future steps, and financing. The workshop gathered participants representing the quintuple helix of the Galician clam and mussel sectors. Full report available at TransformAr D7.5 One video per Demonstrator for Open Days V1 05082025.docx
30/06/2025 17/07/2025 24/10/2025	Complementary Marine Sciences Programme - Workshop - IV Assembly - Final Assembly	28 150 To be held	Present and integrate solutions in the broader marine sciences and policy context. TransformAr is one of the reference projects in the Deliverable 2.1.3 "Informe sobre los riesgos y escenarios de la observación marina en Galicia" (Report on Risks and future Scenarios of Marine Observation in Galicia) Link to news about the workshop and the assemblies:

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avanza o deseño do Plan Estratéxico de Observación Mariña de Galicia coa celebración do segundo obradoiro de validación do seu marco estratéxico - Ciencias Mariñas Galicia - https://galicia.thinkinazul.es/avanza-o-deseno-do-plan-estratexico-de-observacion-marina-de-galicia-coa-celebracion-do-segundo-obradoiro-de-validacion-do-seu-marco-estratexico/ - IPAC Acuicultura
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TransformAr presentation highlights

Consultation Workshop – 24/05/2024

Open Day Galicia – 18/09/2024

Complementary Marine Sciences Programme Workshop – 30/06/2025

Complementary Marine Sciences Programme Assembly – 17/07/2025

1.3 MEDSEA - Sardinia demonstrator

In the Oristano demonstration site, the activities focused on fostering strong engagement among both public and private stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on the fishing sector. Continuous dialogue was ensured through a series of participatory events designed to keep local actors informed about project developments, collect feedback, and enhance awareness of both challenges and potential solutions. These meetings also laid the foundation for the creation of a group of fishermen committed to supporting the maintenance of the monitoring network, ensuring local ownership and continuity of actions.

On the institutional side, three technical roundtables were organized with public authorities responsible for wetland management, fisheries, and water resources. These meetings aimed to strengthen inter-agency cooperation and build a shared framework for post-project management. The overarching goal is to establish a coordinated governance structure capable of ensuring the long-term operation of the Smart Gate and the associated monitoring system, turning TransformAr's pilot experience into a sustainable, locally managed adaptation model.

The following table summarises the main engagement events and technical meetings organised in the Oristano site:

Workshop	Date	Participants	Objective
First workshop Adaptation Pathways (WP3)	11-12 Oct 2022		Introduction of the pathways and CC scenarios
Meetings with fishermen (including 6 presidents of 9 cooperatives and the president of the Consortium, who represents 140 fishermen)	21-4- 2023	16	Pathways validation and discussion with local stakeholders
Internal meeting with CMCC to complete the multicriteria analysis	April 2024	4	Discussion and evaluation of the multicriteria analysis to select the preferred pathway in each KCS
Meetings with fishermen (including 6 presidents of 9 cooperatives and the president of the Consortium, who represents 140 fishermen)	25-3- 2024	12	Validation of multicriteria analysis and identification of the preferred pathway in each KCS
1:1 meeting with Sebastiano Curreli (Agriculture sector) to validate pathways and results of multicriteria analysis	27 March 2024	3	Validation of multicriteria analysis and identification of the preferred pathway in each KCS
1:1 meeting with Andrea Liverani (Agriculture sector) to validate pathways and results of multicriteria analysis	N/A	3	Validation of multicriteria analysis and identification of the preferred pathway in each KCS

Workshop on Action Plan (WP3)	11 May 2024	14	Action plan development
Consultation workshop	14-3-2025	18	Presentation of solution implementation, bankability report and results, market validation questionnaire
First Technical meetings with public entities (WP4)	17-4-2023	14	Strengthen inter-agency cooperation and build a shared framework for post-project management
Second Technical meetings with public entities (WP4)	20-10-2023	N/A	strengthen inter-agency cooperation and build a shared framework for post-project management
Third Technical meetings with public entities (WP4)	4-7-2025	13	strengthen inter-agency cooperation and build a shared framework for post-project management
COAST participatory meetings (WP4) (n. 6 meetings)	multiple days	168	Participatory engagement
Open Day (WP7)	5-7-2024	44	Kids workshop, presentation of the Oristano solution and site visit around the area.
Smart Gate Inauguration inserted in a Living LAB organized in the Interreg Euro-Med Project Wetland4Change (31 total participants of which 9 local stakeholders)	14-5-2025	9	Presentation of the SG solution to the local community
n. 4 Meetings with the Municipality of Terralba	N/A	4	Discussion of specific aspects of the ongoing projects

1.4 Lappeenranta – Finland Demonstrator

Lappeenranta demonstrator's solutions focus on stormwater management, which in Finland is a legislative responsibility of municipalities. As a result, some of the solutions—such as the management of stormwater in public areas (NBS) and the related monitoring (SWMM) are naturally part of the

municipality-owned stormwater network. However, the citizen application (CAF) and choice experiment survey (CEI), can be implemented and maintained by other actors, and NBS solutions can also be used in private areas.

It has also been recognized that residents and private property owners play a significant role in stormwater management in urban areas: actions and stormwater treatment are also needed on private plots to avoid water quality issues in water bodies and overloading of the stormwater sewer system.

In Lappeenranta, the promotion of the solutions has focused on two perspectives: providing residents and other stakeholders with information about climate change adaptation and the solutions implemented to address it, such as NBS, SWMM and CAF as well as utilizing all the knowledge produced in the project (CEI and other results) to develop the services offered by the city and its internal operations.

Events organized by the city of Lappeenranta:

DATE	EVENT	PARTICIPANTS	PURPOSE
2/11/2023-27/5/2024	A total of 5 workshops with stakeholders to explore local climate vulnerability, define solutions, adaptation pathways and an action plan for the city	approx. 10 in each	Determine the climate perspective of local actors, challenges they face, and existing solutions to overcome these challenges. To explore climate vulnerability, impacts and projections. To create vision, solutions and way forward (Construction of Adaptation Pathways). Validation of preferred pathways per KCS and developing adaptation Action Plan.
29/08/2024	Open Day for citizens and other stakeholders	150	Launching citizen application (CAF). Showcasing solutions implemented: organizing guided tours in NBS area, demonstrating real-time monitoring of stormwater quality and providing guidance on citizen science.
26/05/2025	Workshop: market validation, bankability & governance scenarios	11	Market validation of solutions implemented in TransformAr. Reflection on bankability report results. Exploring governance scenarios for NBS.
19/08/2025	Citizen workshop	15	Workshop based on CEI results (willingness to pay): how can citizens start preparing climate change adaptation in their own yard. The aim was to gather citizens' views on the effects of climate change, particularly from the perspective of stormwater risks relevant to residents and private plot owners. To brainstorm ideas on what residents can do to adapt to and prepare for climate change, as well as what support they need from the city.
28/08/2025	Lappeenranta Tänään! (Lappeenranta Today!)	150	Promotion of citizen application (CAF).

	annual stakeholder & citizen event		
24/09/2025	Consultation workshop	10	To discuss the ownership of solutions and the need for cooperation, e.g. between different departments of the city, to implement and maintain the solutions.

Picture from the citizen workshop 19/08/2025, organized by the city of Lappeenranta.

1.5 ADEME – Guadeloupe Demonstrator

The Guadeloupe demonstrator organized several events and workshops with local stakeholders to promote the solutions and support their continuation beyond the project.

DATE	EVENT	PARTICIPANTS	PURPOSE
28/11/2022 & 30/11/2022	Workshop: Adaptation of Guadeloupean Agriculture to Climate Change: Perceptions, Impacts, and Solutions	11 11	<p>The first workshop brought together professionals/farmers from the Guadeloupean agricultural sector, while the second engaged institutional stakeholders from the sector. The objective was to identify the main risks faced by agriculture in Guadeloupe and to develop adaptation pathways that will guide the solutions developed as part of TransformAr.</p> <p>The report of the workshop is available on TransformAr website.</p>
08/12/2022 & 09/12/2022	Workshop: Adaptation of Guadeloupean Tourism to Climate Change: Perceptions, Impacts, and Solutions	12 8	<p>The first workshop brought together operators from the Guadeloupean tourism sector, while the second engaged sectoral experts. The objective was to identify the main risks faced by tourism in Guadeloupe and to develop adaptation pathways that will inform the solutions designed within the TransformAr project.</p> <p>The report of the workshop is available on TransformAr website.</p>
07/04/2023	Workshop: Financing Climate Change	11	<p>Workshop bringing together stakeholders from the tourism and agriculture sectors to assess the financial landscape of climate change adaptation in these two sectors and to outline the</p>

	Adaptation in Guadeloupe		<p>establishment of a Local adaptation fund in Guadeloupe.</p> <p>The report of the workshop is available on TransformAr website.</p>
17/09/2024	Open Day: Agriculture and Tourism Facing Climate Change: How to Finance, How to Raise Awareness	38	<p>The conference provided an interim assessment and explored the long-term sustainability of the Local Adaptation Fund in the agricultural sector.</p> <p>Open Day video</p>
22/05/2025	Consultation Workshop: Financing adaptation for a resilient Guadeloupe: What future for the AF?	21	<p>On May 22, at the initiative of ADEME, stakeholders from the agricultural and tourism sectors in Guadeloupe met to review the lessons learned from the AF, one and a half years after its launch on the archipelago.</p>

The Consultation workshop played a key role in reinforcing the ownership of Guadeloupean solutions, especially the AF. The meeting opened with the presentation of three projects funded by the AF – RESAFOR, PLUVARIDE, and PORC CRÉOLE – illustrating the diversity of supported initiatives.

Two participatory workshops then allowed for deeper discussions:

- **Workshop 1:** Development of a SWOT matrix of the AF, in order to identify its strengths and areas for improvement.
- **Workshop 2:** Building on the previous discussions, two key questions were explored:
 - What process should be considered to evolve towards a one-stop shop?
 - How can stakeholder involvement in the AF scheme be strengthened?

The outcome-based summary of the workshop is available on TransformAr's website.

1.6 City of Egaleo – Athens Demonstrator

Overview of Activities Promoting Ownership of Solutions

Throughout the TransformAr project, the Municipality of Egaleo in partnership with NCSR “Demokritos” actively engaged local communities, youth, educators, and stakeholders in activities designed to promote the ownership of adaptation solutions. The emphasis was on educational engagement, public awareness, and inclusive co-design workshops.

A set of distinct and complementary events were organised to present the implemented solutions (Smart Climate Stations, Demand for Social Services Assessment, Awareness-raising educational programmes, and the Climate Innovation Hub) and invite feedback and participation from the local community. These events focused on fostering understanding of climate-related vulnerabilities and encouraging community-driven contributions to adaptation planning.

Key Events Supporting Solution Ownership

Event 1: TransformAr Workshop: Development of a Shared Vision and Socio-Economic Pathways for a Climate-Resilient Future

Date: 10 October 2022

Location: Participation and Innovation Hub, Municipality of Egaleo

Number of Participants: 17

Organizers: Municipality of Egaleo (MoE) & NCSR “Demokritos”

Purpose of the event:

The workshop was organized as part of Task 3.3 of the TransformAr project to engage local stakeholders in co-developing a shared vision for climate adaptation. The event aimed to identify key climate hazards and vulnerabilities affecting the Municipality of Egaleo and initiate discussions on socio-economic pathways and viable solutions for a resilient future.

Agenda Highlights:

- Introduction to TransformAr and its objectives
- Group exercises on climate risks, vulnerabilities, and potential solutions
- Stakeholder presentations from the Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Education, ASDA, NECCA, schools, and social services
- Polling exercise on future visions and priorities
- Discussion on regional collaboration and the integration of nature-based solutions (NBS)

Solutions Presented / Discussed:

- **Nature-Based Solutions (NBS):** Green infrastructure for water retention and urban cooling
- **Heatwave mitigation:** Use of cool materials, building insulation, and expansion of green spaces

- **Social infrastructure adaptation:** Focus on vulnerable populations such as elderly, children, refugees
- **Water management:** Rainwater harvesting, awareness campaigns on water use and scarcity
- **Educational and awareness-raising measures:** Targeted actions for students and teachers

Outcomes and Key Messages:

- Heatwaves, floods, and droughts identified as the most pressing hazards.
- Stakeholders prioritized NBS and community engagement as key adaptation measures.
- Strong emphasis on the need for collaboration between municipalities and regional authorities.
- A shared understanding was built around the vulnerabilities of schools, elderly homes, and social services to extreme weather events.
- The workshop laid the groundwork for future co-implementation activities, feeding directly into the city's adaptation vision.

Photographic material

Event 2: Adaptation Action Plan Development Workshop

Date: 9 July 2024

Location: Climate Innovation Hub, Municipality of Egaleo

Organised by: Municipality of Egaleo & NCSR "Demokritos"

Number of Participants: 13

Type: Co-Design & Participatory Planning Workshop

Purpose of the event:

This workshop was part of Task 3.5, focusing on the development of the local adaptation action plan. It brought together municipal departments (civil protection, planning, transparency, police, social services), local schools, technical experts, and research institutions. The workshop included detailed presentations of alternative adaptation pathways for Health and Infrastructure, discussion of their transformative potential, and co-development of a feasible and participatory implementation roadmap.

Key Outcomes:

- Agreement on the "blue pathway" as the preferred option for both Health and Infrastructure, given its practicality and stakeholder support.
- Stakeholder validation of the transformative adaptation vision, with specific local priorities identified (e.g., schoolyard greening, support for homeless populations, improved transportation routes, humidity control in buildings).

- Consensus on the need for stronger inter-departmental collaboration, prioritisation of nature-based solutions (NBS), and enhanced citizen engagement.
- Action plan formulation with clearly stated needs (funding, monitoring, cross-department support).

Contributions to ownership:

Participants actively shaped the proposed adaptation solutions, prioritised feasible measures, and expressed commitment to remain involved in future stages. Strong emphasis was placed on connecting implementation to real local needs (e.g., municipal infrastructure, vulnerable groups, school safety). The workshop empowered local actors to align their efforts under a shared climate adaptation vision.

Photographic material

Event 3: Open Green Day

Date: 4 June 2024

Location: Climate Innovation Hub, Municipality of Egaleo

Organizers: Municipality of Egaleo (MoE), NCSR “Demokritos”

Number of participants: 30 local citizens and students

Purpose of the event:

The Open Green Day was designed as a community event to present the TransformAr adaptation solutions implemented in Egaleo and to promote climate awareness through educational and participatory activities. A strong emphasis was placed on youth engagement and the involvement of local schools.

Activities and outcomes:

- Presentation of the main TransformAr solutions deployed in Egaleo, including smart climate stations, citizen engagement apps, demand analysis for social services, and climate education initiatives.
- Participation of local students who presented environmental projects developed during the school year, showcasing data-driven responses to local climate threats (e.g. droughts, heatwaves).
- Organisation of a student hackathon, during which young participants worked in teams to co-design solutions for addressing climate challenges in Egaleo.

- Presentation by NCSR “Demokritos” on past and projected climate risks in the area, including temperature trends and urban vulnerabilities.
- The event contributed to strengthening environmental awareness among younger generations and fostering a sense of climate responsibility.

Follow-up and local impact:

The Open Green Day established a strong connection between the TransformAr project and school-led climate action. By giving visibility to student work and including their voices in public discussions on climate adaptation, the event created momentum for continued engagement with youth as active agents of change. It also reinforced the Climate Innovation Hub's role as a participatory learning space for local citizens.

Photographic material

Event 4. Presentation of Smart Climate Stations (SCS) – RockTheBlock Event

Date: 18 October 2024

Location: Climate Innovation Hub, Municipality of Egaleo

Organizers: Municipality of Egaleo & NCSR Demokritos

Participants: 25

Format: In-person workshop and demonstration

Purpose of the event:

This event focused on the presentation of the Smart Climate Stations (SCS) deployed in Egaleo under the TransformAr project. The aim was to demonstrate how the SCS network functions and how it contributes to the monitoring of local microclimate conditions, particularly in the context of increasing heatwaves and urban heat island (UHI) effects. The event was co-organised by the Municipality of Egaleo and its technical partner NCSR (Demokritos), and took place within the broader framework of the RockTheBlock project activities.

Agenda Highlights:

- Introduction to the TransformAr project

- Overview of Smart Climate Stations (data types, locations, objectives)
- Live demonstration of real-time microclimatic data
- Interactive discussion on integrating SCS data into municipal planning and the RockTheBlock energy retrofitting strategy

Key Outcomes:

- Strong interest from citizens in the accessibility and use of live climate data
- Identification of synergies between SCS and building retrofitting solutions under RockTheBlock
- Expert feedback on the potential integration of SCS data into urban resilience planning tools
- Commitment by local authorities to explore expansion of the SCS network

Photographic material:

Event 5: Participation in the Annual Climate Pact Event (Brussels, 18–19 March 2025)

Date: 18–19 March 2025

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Organisers: European Commission – European Climate Pact

Number of participants: 500+ participants from across Europe

Purpose of the event:

The Annual Climate Pact Event titled *“Together in Action”* brought together climate ambassadors, stakeholders, and EU-funded projects to share progress, engage in collaborative dialogue, and explore new pathways for local and regional climate action. The event offered a platform for reflection on how to scale up citizen and stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation.

Activities and outcomes:

- The Municipality of Egaleo was invited to participate in a high-level panel discussion titled **"Regional perspectives on engaging stakeholders and citizens in climate adaptation planning and implementation"**, alongside representatives of other European initiatives.

- Ms. Evrydiki Pavlidi, Head of European and National Projects at the Directorate of Planning & Transparency of the Municipality of Egaleo, presented the city’s experiences under the **TransformAr project**, with a focus on:
 - Engaging the **educational community** in co-designed adaptation solutions.
 - Empowering **students** through data literacy, hackathons, and climate awareness initiatives.
 - Demonstrating the role of **local government** as a catalyst for climate resilience at the neighbourhood level.
- The intervention showcased **TransformAr’s tools and methods** for citizen involvement and how these can inform broader EU climate engagement strategies.

Follow-up and local impact:

Egaleo’s participation in the Climate Pact event elevated the visibility of its local efforts and opened dialogue with other cities and EU institutions. The presentation reinforced the Municipality’s commitment to youth-driven climate adaptation, while highlighting the importance of embedding educational actions into municipal strategies for long-term resilience.

Photographic material:

Event 6: Consultation Workshop – Egaleo

Date: 30 June 2025

Organisers: Municipality of Egaleo (MoE), in collaboration with NCSR “Demokritos”

Location

Climate Innovation Hub, Egaleo (Greece)

Number of participants: 22 participants

Target group: Local stakeholders, municipal staff, representatives of civil society, youth, educators

Main objective of the event

To gather local feedback on the TransformAr adaptation solutions and to co-reflect on the implementation process and potential future integration into local strategies.

Short description of the event

This workshop was part of the co-implementation and validation phase of the TransformAr project. It aimed at gathering feedback from local stakeholders on the implemented solutions and identifying opportunities for scaling up and sustainability. The event was structured around interactive discussions, presentations of the TransformAr outcomes in Egaleo, and a co-reflection session using digital tools (Mentimeter). Participants shared their views on the effectiveness, usability, and potential of the solutions, and discussed how they could be integrated into broader municipal plans or other ongoing initiatives such as **RockTheBlock** and **MED-IREN**.

The event served as a bridge between project implementation and future policy development, fostering community ownership and inclusivity.

Conclusions

- The solutions implemented under TransformAr were generally well received by the participants, especially those related to climate awareness and educational activities.
- Participants highlighted the importance of continuous community engagement and the integration of such tools into official municipal strategies.
- The workshop offered valuable insights into perceived barriers to uptake (e.g., funding, human resources, political will) and identified possible ways to address them.

Photographic material

The Municipality of Egaleo implemented a diverse and inclusive range of engagement events that fostered local ownership of adaptation solutions under the TransformAr project. Through educational programs, participatory planning workshops, cross-project synergies, and public awareness actions, Egaleo not only strengthened local climate resilience but also ensured that its climate strategies are rooted in community priorities. These efforts will serve as a foundation for future integration of TransformAr solutions into municipal policy and broader replication efforts within and beyond the city.

3.0 Conclusion

Each demonstrator has undertaken stakeholder consultation over time and through this and in instances specific events/workshops at the conclusion of the project have promoted ‘the ownership of solutions’ to encourage upscaling of the solution locally going forward. Demonstrating working examples of solutions is a useful way promote uptake to wider communities, and each demonstrator has its own targeted audience, whether that is embedding the solution with within local authority activities and policy or getting buy in from businesses, water companies and regional actors.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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